

OSCILLATING SPECTRA ASSOCIATED TO CERTAIN SEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT. Certain identities originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences as determinants. In this setting we studied numerically sequences $\{a(n)\}_{n \geq 1}$ derived from the Fourier expansions of cusp forms. We observed that, within the range of our observations, in certain cases the spectra of matrices we attached to these sequences exhibit oscillatory behavior. We collect data on this behavior in some other sequences. We propose that sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may form vector spaces. We initiate testing of this proposal..

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1. INTRODUCTION

Certain identities ([M], Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2 below) originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ with $h_0 = 1$ as determinants $|J_n|$. We studied eigenvalues of the J_n empirically, especially eigenvalues associated to the sequence with $h_n = \tau(p_n)$ for n positive, where tau is Ramanujan's function and p_n denotes the n^{th} prime, because (with our set-up) a zero eigenvalue would entail that $\tau(p_n)$ vanishes. We have not found direct numerical evidence pointing one way or the other in this regard, but after a procedure we will call *deformation*, the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues for a given J_n appears to oscillate in a nearly periodic fashion with n and one hopes, or at least imagines, that this may speak somehow to question. We also saw this behavior in newforms coming from elliptic curves listed in Cremona's database, and in other cusp forms coming from spaces of higher weight and larger dimension, for which the vanishing of coefficients is not an issue; it is common. We also collected data on the eigenvalue behavior of several sequences that do not come from modular forms.

We propose that families of sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may have algebraic structure, and we initiate testing of this proposal. We say that a numerical sequence $\{h_n\}_{n=0,1,\dots}$ with $h_0 = 1$ is *h-coherent* if the minimum moduli among the roots of the characteristic polynomials $\chi(J_n)$ oscillate (as certified by signal-processing tests.) We also say that an arbitrary sequence

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$\{f_n\}$ of polynomials over \mathbb{Q} , whether or not it occurs as a sequence of characteristic polynomials, is *f-coherent* if it is the zero-sequence or if the minimum moduli among the roots of the $\{f_n\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ oscillate. We denote as V_h the set of sequences $\{h_n\}_{n>0}$ such that $\{1, h_1, h_2, \dots\}$ is *h-coherent*, and we write V_f for the set of *f-coherent* sequences $\{f_n\}_{n\geq 0}$. We speculate that V_f and V_h are closed under addition, with sums taken term by term and assembled into sequences. Obviously, closure of V_f under multiplication by a complex number is automatic, so it becomes a vector space over \mathbb{C} if it is additively closed. The situation for V_h in this regard is even less clear, because we do not know whether or not it is closed under multiplication by scalars. Future drafts of this article will address this question. At the time of the present draft, the scope of our tests of additive closure of V_f and V_h is limited, but we have not found counterexamples.

2. LEMMAS

These lemmas appear, for example, in MacDonalD's book [M], but the proofs are not easy to locate; in fact, we have not located them. Home-made proofs of these statements are stored in our repository [Bre25]¹. In the sequel, we denote the cardinality of a set S by $\#S$ and the determinant of a matrix M by $|M|$.

Lemma 2.1. *The equations below are equivalent. (We will refer to both of them as equation (D) in the sequel.) Let $h_0 = 1$ and*

$$(D1) \quad nh_n = \sum_{r=1}^n j_r h_{n-r}$$

for $n \geq 1$. With $H(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} h_n t^n$ and $J(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} j_r t^r$,

$$(D2) \quad t \frac{d}{dt} H(t) = H(t) J(t).$$

With f_0 possibly defined as equal to one, let \bar{f} denote the sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$. Let $J_n(\bar{j})$ and $H_n(\bar{h})$ be the matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -n+1 \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} h_1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 2h_2 & h_1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ nh_n & h_{n-1} & h_{n-2} & \cdots & h_1 \end{pmatrix},$$

¹“Lemmas for ‘Ramanujan’s function on small primes’ ”

respectively.

Lemma 2.2. *Let $h_0 = j_1 = 1$. Equation (D) implies that*

$$(1) \quad j_n = (-1)^{n+1} |H_n(\bar{h})|.$$

and

$$(2) \quad n!h_n = |J_n(\bar{j})|$$

for $n \geq 1$.

Next we state a corollary of the following theorem in Vein and Dale's book [Vein1999].

Proposition 1. *(Vein and Dale, Theorem 4.23) Let $A_n =$*

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & \cdots & a_1 & -(n-1) \\ a_n & a_{n-1} & \cdots & a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}^T,$$

where the T operator is matrix transpose. Let $B_n(x) = |A_n - xI_n|$, so that $B_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi_{A_n}(x)$. Then

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |A_r| x^{n-r}.$$

The corollary is the following

Theorem 2.3. ² *With h and j as in the above lemmas,*

$$\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}.$$

Proof. Determinants are invariant under the transpose, so, setting each a_i equal to j_i in the lemmas above, the proposition can be restated in the following way: Let $J_n(\bar{j}) =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -(n-1) \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & \cdots & j_2 & j_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $C_n(x) = |(J_n(\bar{j}) - xI_n|$, so that $C_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x)$. By Proposition 1, $C_n(x) =$

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |J_r(\bar{j})| (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r} =$$

²Here we are merely codifying an argument shown to us by J. López-Bonilla. See also the personal communication of Petović to the author *Petović's proof* [Bre25].

(by Lemma 2.2)

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-x)^{n-r} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r}.$$

Simplifying, $\chi((J_n(\vec{j}))(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r(-1)^r x^{n-r}$. \square

Remark 1. This result allows us to bypass the calculation of determinants, resulting in a marked speedup, when computing the polynomials χ . So far we have applied it in Figure 2B below. Its implementation is described in Remark 3 below.

Now let M be an $n \times n$ matrix over a field. For any subset $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, let $M[S, S]$ denote the submatrix of M with rows and columns indexed by S . The following proposition is well known. (For example, see equation (1.2.13) in Horn and Johnson's book [Horn2012].)

Proposition 2. *The coefficient a_k of x^k in $\chi(M)$ satisfies*

$$a_{n-k} = (-1)^k \sum_{\substack{\#S=k \\ S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}}} |M[S, S]|.$$

Remark 2. In this article, we seek sufficient conditions, using the machinery of this section, to establish that particular sequences $\{h_n\}_{n=1, 2, \dots}$ are non-vanishing. For example, let $h_0 = 1$ and $h_n = \tau(n)$ when n is positive. Let $\{j_n\}_{n=1, 2, \dots}$ be the sequence paired with h in equation (D1) above. Now let n be positive. Then $\chi(J_n(\vec{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $|J_n(\vec{j})| = 0$, so, by Lemma 2.2.2, $\chi(J_n(\vec{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $\tau(n) = 0$. Now if $\chi(J_n(\vec{j}))$ is irreducible over the rational numbers, zero is not a root of $\chi(J_n(\vec{j}))(x)$ and $\tau(n) \neq 0$. A similar argument works if we consider the sequence for which $h_n = \tau(p_n)$ when n is positive.

We will not focus on this kind of sufficient condition in the sequel. We mention it because it is the only such condition we know at the time of the present draft. Instead we explore a geometric phenomenon: under certain conditions, which so far we cannot crisply describe, the eigenvalues of “deformed” versions of the $\chi(J_n(x))$ (defined in the next section) appear to oscillate as point sets as n increases. We would like to gain control over this and use it to bound the distance of these eigenvalues away from zero for certain sequences h , then to devise a version of the argument to bound the eigenvalues of the original (“undeformed”) matrices away from zero as well. This seems to be a challenging task. What we would like to do at this stage is simply to understand what it is about the $\chi(J_n(x))$ that induces the observed oscillations (when in fact they do so.) We have collected lists of these characteristic polynomials for some sequences h (Fourier coefficients of modular forms), which are available to the interested reader in data files generated in the SageMath *Jupyter* notebooks in our repository [Bre25]. We have not found a way to predict whether the relevant plots oscillate simply

from characteristics of the modular forms that they come from. We speculate that first we need to learn how to make such predictions from basic features of the characteristic polynomials.

3. THE SEQUENCES $\{p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ AND $\{\tau(p_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$

For a sequence $S = \{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$, let $S^{(c)} = \{c, x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j}) = J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})$ and $H_n^{(c)}(\bar{h}) = H_n(\overline{h^{(c)}})$. We refer to them as *deformations* of the matrices $H_n(\bar{h})$ and $J_n(\bar{j})$. We will freely abuse the notation by employing the H, h, J , and j symbols to denote objects in a way that depends on the context.

Remark 3. The most straightforward workflow to find $\chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}}))$ for a given member of a sequence $\{h_n^{(c)}\}_n$ may be (concisely) diagrammed as follows:

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow J_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

The code in most of the *Jupyter* notebooks cited in the index of the present draft follows this pattern, but in our recent experience the following workflow is more efficient.

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{(D1)} h_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{Th.2.3} \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

(So far we have applied it only in a few figures.)

3.1. The sequence $\{\tau(p)\}_{p \text{ prime}}$ and its developments. Let p_n denote the n^{th} prime. It will be convenient to write $\tau_p(n) := \tau(p_n)$, $h(0) = 1$ and $h(n) = \tau_p(n)$ for positive integers n . We define a sequence \bar{j} by requiring $j(n)$ and $h(n)$ together to satisfy equation (D). By Lemma 2.2 (2), $\tau(p_n) = |J_n(\bar{j})|/n!$. Let $\Pi_n(x) = \chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = |xI - J_n(\bar{j})|$ be the characteristic polynomial of $J_n(\bar{j})$. Plots 3 and 4 show the behavior of the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues of $\Pi_n^{(1)}$ and Π_n respectively. They are relevant to Lehmer's question because the following statements are equivalent:

- (a) $\tau(p_n) = 0$,
- (b) $|J_n(\bar{j})| = 0$, and
- (c) $\Pi_n(0) = 0$.

Remark 4. Writing³ $\Pi_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,n-k} x^{n-k}$, Theorem 2.3 gives

$$(3) \quad a_{n,n-k} = (-1)^k k! \binom{n}{k} \tau(p_k).$$

Remark 5. The number of terms in the sum in Proposition 2 is $\binom{n}{k}$, so the simplest way to reconcile Proposition 2 and equation (3) is to suppose that the structural symmetries of $J_n(\bar{j})$ somehow force $|J_n(\bar{j})[S, S]| = (-1)^k k! \tau(p_k)$ just when $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\#S = k$. But this turns out to be too good to be true.⁴ Instead, there must be systematic cancellations coming from those symmetries. So far, we have not understood these cancellations.

³See 'undeformed tauprime2nov25no3.ipynb' in the repository [Bre25].

⁴See 'too good.ipynb' in [Bre25].

3.2. Characteristic functions of the deformed matrices $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j})$ representing the sequence $\{\tau(p_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$. For the sequence $\{j\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ and the matrices $J_n(\bar{j})$ of the preceding subsection, let $\chi(J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j})) = \Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ (say.) Let $E_n^{(c)}$ be the set of zeros of $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ and let $\mu_n^{(c)} = \min_{v \in E_n^{(c)}} |v|$; then it appears that the graph of the pairs $(n, \mu_n^{(c)})$ lies on an oscillating curve for $1 \leq c \leq 3$ (see Figures 2, 3 and 4). As a control, we repeated the calculation for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$ for $c = 1$. Figure 6 shows the resulting plot. It shows no oscillatory behavior for this choice of h , suggesting that the choice of prime indices *per se* was decisive. (See Remark 6 below, however, for our own reservations about this argument.) The deep spikes in the lower, logarithmic plot in Figure 2A suggest that the approach of the roots of $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ to the origin may behave in a predictable way, but the details are not clear to us because (among other reasons) our data is limited. We do not know the details of the relationship of the roots of $\Pi_n(x)$ to those of the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$, so the connection, if any, to Lehmer's question is unclear.

The lower envelope of the lower plot of logarithms of minimum moduli for each n in $\{2, 3, \dots, 400\}$ displayed in Figure 3 appear to behave regularly: the abscissas of the points on the lower envelope form a set $\{5, 9, \dots, 395\}$, which, when they are replaced by their residues modulo 4, make Table 1. The size of the blocks of equal residues are 10 for the first one and 9 for each of the others.⁵

For contrast, we reproduce in Figure 7 a plot of the minimum moduli for each n for the undeformed characteristic polynomials $\Pi_n(x)$. We have not attempted the sort of analysis we just discussed for the $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$.

We want a global-in- c understanding of the deformed plots. After prepending c to \bar{j}_{τ_p} , denoting this deformation as $\bar{j}_{\tau_p}^{(c)}$ and once more applying equation (D1), we computed a sequence $\bar{h}_{\tau_p}^{(c)}$ from $\bar{j}_{\tau_p}^{(c)}$. We formed the list of pairs $(c, n!h^{(c)}(n))$. (These are just the values of the determinants from Lemma 2.2 in this situation; but now we can bypass calculating the determinants and by that expedient achieve significant time savings.) We found that, within the range of our observations, these pairs interpolate a polynomial D_n (say) of degree n . For given n , we found the minimum modulus among the roots of D_n and plotted these minima against n . In the case $c \in \mathbb{Z}^{\geq 0}$, the result was the same kind of oscillating wave form that the first few individual values of c exhibit, as we see in Figure 5.⁶

⁵We are using data from the lower envelope of the logarithms of the minimum moduli. (The lower plot in Figure 3.) See “tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.ipynb” in [Bre25].

⁶See Table 7 below and notebook ‘tauprime many c’s 18feb26’ in [Bre25]. The reader will notice that we ran the routines twice, at 64-bit and 100-bit precision. The results were indistinguishable.

4. OSCILLATORY BEHAVIOR IN NEWFORMS FROM ELLIPTIC CURVES

Because the cusp form Δ is the generating function of the multiplicative Ramanujan function, which displays oscillatory behavior in the range of our observations, we searched a source of cusp forms that are generating functions of other multiplicative functions: Cremona's database [LMFDB] of cusp forms $\sum_n a(n)q^n$ associated to elliptic curves in virtue of the Modularity Theorem. We found similar oscillatory behavior. (But see the next section for examples of oscillatory behavior coming from cusp forms the coefficient functions of which are not multiplicative.)

The forms in Cremona's database have weight two and varying levels.⁷ In the limited range of our observations, there is much variation in the oscillatory behavior, or lack of it, in deformed curves.

In contrast to the inclusion of plots of the logarithms of minimum moduli among eigenvalues associated to matrices representing Ramanujan's original tau function, we omit such plots for the curves in Cremona's database. The logarithm plots in the former situation served to demonstrate that the minima were not hitting zero, but for the Cremona database curves, they must occasionally do so, because the corresponding Fourier coefficients $a(n)$ themselves occasionally vanish. Table 3 (incomplete right now) summarizes our Fourier analysis at deformation parameter $c = 1$.⁸

Remark 6. Among our figures we have plots of eigenvalue minimum moduli for the sequences $h(n) = a(n)$ and $h(n) = a(p_n)$, but also for the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$. Our original intention was to introduce controls like the one we described above, which was meant to provide some evidence for the thesis that the $\tau(p_n)$ were producing oscillations because of arithmetic characteristics of the inputs. We expected to see a pattern in which the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n)$ induced oscillations among the minimal eigenvalues, and the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ did not, but there is no such pattern. This undercuts the rationale behind our original controls for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$. We have carried forward all controls into this article anyway, for obvious reasons.

5. CUSP FORMS FROM SPACES OF WEIGHT EXCEEDING TWO

We have begun to test for oscillatory behavior among cusp forms belonging to spaces of weight greater than two. Some Hecke eigenforms in such spaces have non-rational Fourier expansions. Decimal estimates of their coefficients carry error that could explode in our calculations. To avoid this issue, we examined the sums of the eigenforms over the automorphisms of their coefficient fields that fix \mathbb{Q} (the traces.) These objects have rational expansions.

⁷SageMath notebooks corresponding to Table 4 are in [Bre25].

⁸The analysis of the curve $\tau(p_n), c = 0$ was carried out in the notebook 'deformed c=0 primetau3feb26' and that of the curve " $\tau(p_n), c = 1$ ", was done in the notebook 'tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25', both stored in [Bre25].

To explain this, we sketch Hecke theory up to the definition of newforms. Denoting the space of cusp forms at level N and weight k as $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$, for $f, g \in S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ the Petersson inner product is defined as $\langle f, g \rangle =$

$$\int_{\Gamma_0(N)\backslash\mathfrak{H}} f(z)\overline{g(z)}y^k \frac{dx dy}{y^2}.$$

Let $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the subspace of all linear combinations of $f(dz)$ where $f \in S_k(\Gamma_0(M))$ for some $M|N$ with $M < N$ and $d|(N/M)$. Let $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the orthogonal complement of $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with respect to the Petersson inner product. Then $S_k(\Gamma_0(N)) = S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N)) \oplus S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$.

Let T_1 be the identity operator on $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ and, for primes $p \nmid N$, let the Hecke operator T_p satisfy

$$T_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(a_{pn} + p^{k-1} a_{n/p} \right) q^n,$$

where $a_{n/p} = 0$ if $p \nmid n$. For $e \geq 2$, let $T_{p^e} = T_p T_{p^{e-1}} - p^{k-1} T_{p^{e-2}}$.

For prime divisors p of N , let the operator U_p satisfy

$$U_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} a_{pn} q^n,$$

and set $U_{p^e} = U_p^e$ where the exponent on the right side means repeated composition. For $n = \prod_p p^{e_p}$, let $T_n = \prod_{p \nmid N} T_{p^{e_p}} \cdot \prod_{p|N} U_{p^{e_p}}$. A *newform* in $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ is a cusp form $f \in S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with $a_1(f) = 1$ that is a simultaneous eigenvector for all Hecke operators T_p for $p \nmid N$ and for all U_p such that $p | N$.

We consider a separate linear map to extract rational expansions from the newforms. For v in a vector space V and a linear map $\mu : V \rightarrow V$, let $\text{tr}(\mu)$ be sum of the eigenvalues of μ . For a finite extension of fields L/K viewed as a vector space over K , let $\mu_\alpha(v) = \alpha v$. We write $\text{Tr}_{L/K}(\alpha) = \text{tr}(\mu_\alpha)$ and consider a finite extension E/\mathbb{Q} such that all of the Fourier coefficients in the expansion of a newform f lie in E . E/\mathbb{Q} is separable, so we may write $E = \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ for some α in E by the Primitive Element Theorem. It is well known that $\text{Tr}_{E/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$ is rational.⁹

In our first example, we inspected the unique-up-to-conjugacy newform f in $S_4(\Gamma_0(11))$, whose coefficient field is $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ with $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 2 = 0$ (so $\alpha = 1 \pm \sqrt{3}$). The space has dimension 2 and a single orbit under μ_α of degree 2. We carried out our usual procedures for the sequences $h_{\text{all}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_n(f))$ and $h_{\text{primes}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_{p_n}(f))$, setting $h_{\text{all}}(0) = h_{\text{primes}}(0) = 1$ to conform to equation (D). The minimum-modulus eigenvalue plots for our J matrices are shown in Figure 42. The function $n \mapsto h_{\text{all}}(n)$ is not multiplicative on positive n , and this is the first such example with oscillatory behavior that we have found.

⁹For example, combine [Orr] (Lemma 19) and [Marcus] (corollary to Theorem 4'.)

6. OTHER SEQUENCES

We do not understand the pattern of occurrences of oscillations among the minimum moduli plotted in the figures below. We have searched unsuccessfully for predictive criteria among the characteristics of the modular forms in our numerical experiments. Now we are looking for such criteria among the characteristic polynomials. We are guessing that such criteria, if there are any, will be easier to spot for sequences h that are constructed as simply as possible. As a beginning, in Figures 48 and 49 we display minimum moduli plots for the sequences $\{p_{n+1} - p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{p_{n+1} - p_n - 2\}_{n \geq 1}$, and $\{n^a\}_{n \geq 1}$, $a = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

7. TESTS OF ADDITIVE CLOSURE

Obviously the presence of oscillatory behavior, or its lack, is determined by polynomial spectra. We use Fourier analytic methods to certify the presence of this behavior. Writing code for signal analysis is not within the present writer's competence, so he relied for this on the AI model Claude [Anthropic2026]. The code is in our repository [Bre25] under the title "Fourier analysis of minimum moduli". A guide by Claude to the interpretation of the reports generated by this code is also stored there under the title "v9 interpretation guide". These reports include a significance score for the first-ranked period of the plot under consideration, which for most of our tests is 99%. But in some cases (for example, that of Chebyshev polynomials, no period passes the relevant statistical tests, yet the report summary issues the verdict "PERIODIC" on the basis of another parameter, ACF strength.

Tests of additive closure for V_f are illustrated in Figure 50. We keep track of ongoing tests of V_f closure in Table 2 and of V_h closure in Table 3. (In the code for columns of Table 2 labeled "Plot 1" and "Plot 2", unlike the column "Sum plot", there is no need to take an extra step to extract the list of polynomials. It is just the list of characteristic polynomials.) For the purpose of these tests, we are going to count as h - or f -coherent any sequence that is certified PERIODIC.

We now describe the work flows in the code that produced the tables. Let $E(f_n)$ be the set of zeros of a polynomial f_n and let $\mu_n = \min_{v \in E(f_n)} |v|$. The code for each plot among our figures takes as input a numerical sequence $\{h(n)\}_n$, associates to it a sequence of characteristic polynomials $\{\chi_n\}_n$ in accordance with our lemmas, and creates a list of pairs $\{(n, \mu_n)\}_n$. Finally, the list of pairs is graphed. So the work flow for a given n to generate the original figures may be sketched as follows:

$$h(n) \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n.$$

That the polynomial sequences $\{f_n\}_n$ we test for membership in V_f are typically characteristic polynomials of certain matrices in the present setting is only happenstance. What is required is a supply of f -coherent sequences, and a plot exhibiting oscillatory spectra is generated by a workflow that

includes a sequence $\{\chi_n\}_n$ which (if we believe our signal-processing) is f -coherent.

The code collects the sequences $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of the figures as certified by our Fourier analyses. Because those two plots showed oscillatory behavior, $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ are f -coherent by definition; this is their crucial property for Table 2. The process recorded in Table 2 tests whether or not their sum $\{\chi_n + \chi'_n\}_n$ which is not necessarily a sequence of characteristic polynomials at all, is also f -coherent. If it is, we are looking at an instance of V_f additive closure. The point of compiling Table 2 is to find out whether not we will always see additive closure in these circumstances. Any instance where we do not would refute the hypothesis that V_f is closed under addition.

The code for Table 3 collects h -coherent sequences $\{h_n\}_n$ and $\{h'_n\}_n$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of our figures, as certified by our Fourier analyses. It forms a third sequence $\{h_n + h'_n\}_n =$ (say) $\{h''\}_n$ and executes the full work flow

$h''(n) \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n$, plots the pairs (n, μ_n) , and tests for oscillatory behavior using Fourier methods. In other words, the code tests whether or not $\{h''\}_n$ is h -coherent. (The sequences $\{h_n\}_n$ and $\{h'_n\}_n$ are modified to form the sequence $\{h''\}_n$. We set $h_0 = h'_0 = 1/2$, so that $h''_0 = 1$ in conformance with our lemmas.)

Both tables display the relevant significance scores for each plot.

8. TABLES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of tables after the bibliography.

1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3			

TABLE 1. Residues modulo 4 of abscissas from the lower envelope of Figure 2.

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 50A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 50B
3	Fig. 2B	Fig. 8C	Fig. 50C

TABLE 2. Successful tests for additive closure of V_f . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 50A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 50B

TABLE 3. Successful tests for additive closure of V_h . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

9. FIGURES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of figures after the bibliography.

FIGURE 1. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(n)$ with $c = 0$.

FIGURE 2. $c = 1, h(n) = \tau(p_n)$

MINIMUM MÖDULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 3. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ with $c = 2$.

FIGURE 4. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ with $c = 3$.

MINIMUM MODULI

LOG MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 5. Minimum moduli over many values of c for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 6. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$ with $c = 1$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 7. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ before deformation.

FIGURE 8. Cremona curve 11a1.

FIGURE 9. Cremona curve 14a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 10. Cremona curve 15a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 11. Cremona curve 17a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 12. Cremona curve 19a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 13. Cremona curve 20a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 14. Cremona curve 21a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 15. Cremona curve 24a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 16. Cremona curve 26a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 17. Cremona curve 26b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 18. Cremona curve 27a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 19. Cremona curve 30a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 20. Cremona curve 32a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 21. Cremona curve 33a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 22. Cremona curve 34a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 23. Cremona curve 35a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 24. Cremona curve 36a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 25. Cremona curve 37a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 26. Cremona curve 37b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 27. Cremona curve 38a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 28. Cremona curve 38b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 29. Cremona curve 39a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 30. Cremona curve 40a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 31. Cremona curve 42a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 32. Cremona curve 43a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 33. Cremona curve 44a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 34. Cremona curve 45a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 35. Cremona curve 46a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 36. Cremona curve 48a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 37. Cremona curve 49a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 38. Cremona curve 50a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 39. Cremona curve 50b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 40. Cremona curve 51a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 41. Cremona curve 53a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 42. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 1, weight 16.

FIGURE 43. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 4.

FIGURE 44. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 6.

FIGURE 45. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 4.

FIGURE 46. Sum over the first of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 47. Sum over the second of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 48. Prime differences deformed with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 49. $h(n) = n^a, 1 \leq a \leq 4$ with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 50. V_f additive closure tests (minimum moduli for roots of the sums of characteristic polynomials) from Column 3 (“Sum plot”) of Table 2

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10. APPENDIX 1: INDEX OF FIGURES

The notebooks are in our repository [Bre25].

Figure	Notebook
Figure 1	Fig 1 deformed tau c = 0 25may26
Figure 2A	tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25
Figure 2B	Fig 2B tauprime c=1 25may26
Figure 3	Fig 3 tauprime c=2 25may26
Figure 4	Fig 4 tauprime c=3 25may26
Figure 5	Fig 5 tauprime many c’s 25may26
Figure 6	tauprime controls 6april26
Figure 7	undeformed primeTau 6april26
Figure 8A	Fig 8A curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 8B	curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 27mar26
Figure 8C	Fig 8C curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25may26
Figure 8D	undeformed curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 4may26
Figure 8E	undeformed curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 5may26
Figure 8F	undeformed curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 5may26
Figure 9A	Fig 9A curve 14a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 9B	curve 14a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 16april26
Figure 9C	Fig 9C curve 14a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25may26
Figure 10A	Fig 10A curve 15a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 10B	curve 15a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 28mar26
Figure 10C	Fig 10C curve 15a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25may26
Figure 11A	curve 17a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 5april26
Figure 11B	Fig 11B curve 17a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 25may26
Figure 11C	Fig 11C curve 17a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25may26
Figure 12A	Fig 12A curve 19a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 12B	curve 19a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 8april26
Figure 12C	curve 19a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 13A	Fig 13A curve 20a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 13B	Fig 13B curve 20a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 25may26
Figure 13C	curve 20a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 14A	curve 21a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 19mar26
Figure 14B	Fig 14B curve 21a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 25may26

Figure	Notebook
Figure 14C	Fig 14C curve 21a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25mar26
Figure 15A	Fig 15A curve 24a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 25may26
Figure 15B	Fig 15B curve 24a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 25may26
Figure 15C	curve 24a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 16A	Fig 16A curve 26a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 16B	Fig 16B curve 26a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 16C	Fig 16C curve 26a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 26may26
Figure 17A	Fig 17A curve 26b1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26mar26
Figure 17B	Fig 17B curve 26b1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 17C	curve 26b1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 18A	Fig 18A curve 27a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 18B	Fig 18B curve 27a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 18C	Fig 18C curve 27a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 26may26
Figure 19A	Fig 19A curve 30a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 19B	Fig 19B curve 30a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 19C	Fig 19C curve 30a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 26may26
Figure 20A	Fig 20A curve 32a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 20B	Fig 20B curve 32a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 20C	curve 32a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 21A	Fig 21A curve 33a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 21B	Fig 21B curve 33a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 21C	curve 33a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 4april26
Figure 22A	Fig 22A curve 34a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 22B	curve 34a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 12mar26
Figure 22C	curve 34a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 23A	curve 35a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 19mar26
Figure 23B	Fig 23B curve 35a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 23C	curve 35a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 24A	Fig 24A curve 36a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 24B	Fig 24B curve 36a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 24C	curve 36a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 25A	Fig 25A curve 37a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 25B	curve 37a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 11mar26
Figure 25C	Fig 25C curve 37a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 26may26
Figure 26A	curve 37b1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 19mar26
Figure 26B	Fig 26B curve 37b1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 26C	curve 37b1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 15mar26
Figure 27A	curve 38a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 19mar26
Figure 27B	Fig 27B curve 38a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 27C	Fig 27C curve 38a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 26may26
Figure 28A	Fig 28A curve 38b1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26
Figure 28B	Fig 28B curve 38b1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 26may26
Figure 28C	curve 38b1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 29A	Fig 29A curve 39a1 $h(n) = a(n)$ 26may26

Figure	Notebook
Figure 29B	curve 39a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 12mar26
Figure 29C	curve 39a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 30A	curve 40a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 20mar26
Figure 30B	curve 40a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 13mar26
Figure 30C	curve 40a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 31A	curve 42a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 20mar26
Figure 31B	curve 42a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 13mar26
Figure 31C	curve 42a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 32A	curve 43a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 20mar26
Figure 32B	curve 43a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 11mar26
Figure 32C	curve 43a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 33A	curve 44a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 20mar26
Figure 33B	curve 44a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 13mar26
Figure 33C	curve 44a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 34A	curve 45a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 20mar26
Figure 34B	curve 45a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 13mar26
Figure 34C	curve 45a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16mar26
Figure 35A	curve 46a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 21mar26
Figure 35B	curve 46a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 35C	curve 46a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 36A	curve 48a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 21mar26
Figure 36B	curve 48a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 36C	curve 48a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 37A	curve 49a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 11april26
Figure 37B	curve 49a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 37C	curve 49a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 38A	curve 50a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 21april26
Figure 38B	curve 50a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 38C	curve 50a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 39A	curve 50b1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 11april26
Figure 39B	curve 50b1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 39C	curve 50b1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 40A	curve 51a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 21mar26
Figure 40B	curve 51a1 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14mar26
Figure 40C	curve 51a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 41A	curve 53a1 indexed $h(n) = a(n)$ 21mar26
Figure 41B	curve 53a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 11mar26
Figure 41C	curve 53a1 indexed $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 17mar26
Figure 42A	N=1, k=16, $h(n) = a(n)$ 13april26
Figure 42B	N=1, k=16 $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 8apr26
Figure 42C	N=1, k =16, $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 9april26
Figure 43A	N=5, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(n)$ 10april26
Figure 43B	N=5, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 2april26
Figure 43C	N=5, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 3april26

Figure	Notebook
Figure 44A	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(n)$ 10april26
Figure 44B	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 10april26
Figure 44C	N=5, k=6 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 11april26
Figure 45A	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(n)$ 12april26
Figure 45B	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 15april26
Figure 45C	N=11, k=4 cuspfrm $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 30mar26
Figure 46A	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(n)$ 12april26
Figure 46B	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 14april26
Figure 46C	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[0] $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 14april26
Figure 47A	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(n)$ 15april26
Figure 47B	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(p_n)$ 16april26
Figure 47C	N=11, k=6 cuspfrm orbit[1] $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 16april26
Figure 48A	prime diffs c=1 18may26
Figure 48B	Figure 48B pph c=1 27may26
Figure 49A	charpol tests $h(n) = n$ 21may26
Figure 49B	charpol tests $h(n) = n^2$ 20may26
Figure 49C	charpol tests $h(n) = n^3$ 21may26
Figure 49D	charpol tests $h(n) = n^4$ 22may26
Figure 50A	Fig 2B + Fig 48B charpols 25may26
Figure 50B	Fig 16C + Fig 17A charpols 25may26

11. APPENDIX 2: INDEX OF TABLES

See the following notebooks in our repository [Bre25]. Their file names should be self-explanatory:

11.1. **Table 1.** Notebook:

tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.

11.2. **Table 2.** Notebooks:

Fig 2B no3 29may26

Fig 48B pph c=1 30may26

Fig 2B + Fig 48B charpols 30may26

Fig 16C no3 29may26

Fig 17A no3 27may26

Fig 16C + Fig 17A charpols 30may26

Fig 8C curve 11a1 $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ 25may26

Fig 2B + Fig 8C charpols 31may26

11.3. **Table 3.** Notebooks:

$h_{2B} + h_{48B}$ closure 27may26

$h_{16C} + h_{17A}$ closure 28may26

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